

The mighty power of purple bacteria

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Introduction

Photosynthesis – carried out by plants, algae, and some bacteria – is the sole biological process on Earth able to convert sunlight into other forms of energy. Evolutionary studies, supported by comparative genomics, have provided insights into the switch from ancestral anoxygenic to oxygenic photosynthesis. This event heavily influenced the atmosphere of Earth during the Great Oxidation as a consequence of the metabolism of O₂-producing cyanobacteria [1, 2].

Yet, anoxygenic photosynthetic organisms colonize several contemporary natural environmental niches with a wide range of sulfur and nonsulfur green and purple bacteria belonging to four different clades [3]. These bacteria have been investigated as model systems for the comprehension of the molecular mechanisms of photosynthesis. One of the most investigated photosynthetic anoxygenic microorganisms [4] is the purple non-sulfur bacterium *Rhodobacter* (*R.*) *sphaeroides* recently reclassified as *Cereibacter sphaeroides* [5] belonging to the family Paracoccaceae in the class α -proteobacteria. For sake of simplicity, in the following text previous classification will be maintained. The wild type strain *R. sphaeroides* 2.4.1 is able to thrive in several environmental conditions thanks to its versatile metabolism that include respiration, fermentation and photosynthesis. Exposure to light at low oxygen concentration induces the formation of membrane invaginations called intracytoplasmic membranes (ICM) protruding toward the cytoplasm. These are very specialized portion of the bacteria [6] where all the molecular machineries required for photosynthesis and the relevant cofactors are localized, including the photochemical core formed by two light-harvesting complexes (LH1 and LH2) and the photochemical enzyme called reaction center (RC) [7]. The RC is a membrane-spanning photoenzyme composed by three protein subunits and nine cofactors arranged in two quasi-symmetric branches named A and B [8].

Light is absorbed by the LH system and the collected excitation energy is transferred to the RC where the photochemical energy transduction is accomplished. Eventually, with a yield close to 1, each photon transferred to the RC is converted in an electron-hole couple with a lifetime that spans from 100 of milliseconds to a few seconds depending on the environmental conditions of the RC. The charge-separated state obtained from the photochemical conversion within the RC is the driving force for the metabolism of the bacterium. The RC can be easily isolated from the microorganisms, purified, and handled in quite simple experimental conditions. It can be regarded as a “biological semiconductor” in which electrons are promoted, by photon absorption, from the valence to the conduction bands, with an efficiency of the electron-hole pair formation close to unity.

Artificial antennas

The isolated RC have absorption peaks distributed along the entire region spanning from 240 nm and 1000 nm. Yet, some absorption gaps are present between 600-700 nm and, as shown in Figure 1b in the case of the R26 mutant, between 450-540 nm. In isolated RC, the light harvesting ability of RC can be boosted by using specific artificial light absorbing antennas. The bioconjugation of RC

with specifically organic molecules designated to act as artificial antennas can be potentially useful for the generation of devices for photovoltaics and biosensing. Lysines [9] and cysteines [10], a common target in the bioconjugation of proteins and enzymes with organic moieties, have been used to bind the RC to a series of artificial synthetic antennas. The resulting biohybrid systems demonstrate the possibility to enhance the photoconversion efficiency of the enzyme working upon both monochromatic and white light excitation.

The proof-of-concept was obtained with the organic fluorophore AE600 (Fig. 1a) that was designed to fulfill the spectroscopic, chemical, and steric requirements to act as an artificial antenna for the RC. It absorbs light at 450 nm (where the RC absorption is at a minimum) and has a large Stokes shift with an emission maximum at 602 nm, which corresponds to an RC absorption peak. This extends the range of wavelengths for energy photoconversion where the RC does not efficiently absorb (Fig. 1b). At 450 nm, the photocycle of the photoenzyme was found to be almost three times faster in the AE–RC than in the unmodified protein (Fig. 1c). This result not only confirms that the bioconjugation is not detrimental to the protein activity but, more importantly, that it enhances the ability of the RC to drive the photocycle [9].

Figure 1. **a** Chemical structure of AE600: bis(thiophene)benzothiadiazole core with two phenylethynylene arms and a succinimidyl ester group for selective conjugation of lysines in RC. **b** Absorption spectra of RC and AE. Fluorescence spectrum of AE. RC (1 μM), AE (4 μM) in Tris (20 mM), EDTA (1 mM), TX-100 (0.03 %, pH 8; TTE buffer). **c** Light driven cytochrome c oxidation at 450 nm for RC and AE–RC. Photon flux= $1.50 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{E s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$. RC or AE–RC (0.5 μM), Cytochrome c (5 μM), decyl-quinone (50 μM) in TTE buffer with KCl (100 mM). From *Angew. Chem.* 2012 Int. Ed., 51: 11019-11023.

AE750 (Fig. 2a) is characterized by a maximum absorption red-shifted compared to AE600. This molecule bears a core composed of two ethylenedioxythiophene units and a bis-p-tolylsubstituted thiazole-quinoxaline central ring. A further phenylene ethynylene unit is bound to the core, ending with a flexible alkyl spacer and a succinimidyl ester suitable as an activating group towards the bioconjugation of amino groups of RC lysines. An absorbance enhancement in the visible region (350-450 nm and 500-700 nm) was recorded as an effect of the antenna absorption bands. In this case the photoactivity of AE750-RC is 3.5 and 2.1 times higher than that of the native RC when illuminating with the same photon flux at 450 and 650 nm respectively [11].

AE800 (Fig. 2b) is characterized by a broader absorption spectrum as compared to A750 and AE600. Furthermore the absorption peaks remain centered in the absorption gaps of the RC while its emission overlaps the most intense RC absorption bands in the Near Infrared region of the spectrum, ensuring a consistent increase of the protein optical cross section. The energy collected

by the artificial antenna is transferred to the protein via FRET mechanism, and the hybrid system outperforms by a noteworthy 30% the overall photochemical activity of the native protein under the entire range of visible light. In this case the outcome is that AE800-RC outperforms RC by a factor of 5.1 and 2.7 at 450 and 650 nm, respectively [12].

Figure 2. **a** Chemical structure of the artificial antennas AE750 and **b** AE800.

With the aim to further enhance the photoconversion efficiency of RC in the visible range of excitation, the attention was recently shifted to the class of antenna molecules bearing an heptamethine cyanine backbone. Cy-3 and Cy-4 cyanines were synthesized by a nucleophilic substitution of the central chlorine atom in IR-820 and IR-780 with 4-(methylamino)butanoic acid. This reaction allows the molecules to be functionalized with a flexible alkyl spacer that would reduce their sterical hindrance on the protein surface and a pending carboxyl group suitable for their bioconjugation to the protein. The resulting Cy-3 and Cy-4 products are soluble in water/detergent solutions and show broad absorption spectrum in the visible region [13], thus fulfilling some requirements of organic molecules designed to be used as RC light harvesting antennas (Fig. 3) improving the $45\pm 2\%$ in the yield of the charge-separated state formation of RC [14, 15].

Figure 3. **a)** Chemical structure of the hCyN7-NHS organic antenna sketched in close proximity to the residue lysine M110 **b)** Schematic drawing of the RC (PDB ID: 1AIJ) of *R. sphaeroides* with nine cofactors in the A and B branches. The lysine residue targets for the bioconjugation reaction are drawn as van der Waals spheres (carbon in green and nitrogen in blue). **c)** Optical absorption spectra of the RC (black), hCyN7 (red), and emission spectrum of hCyN7 (blue). The absence of carotenoid molecules bound to the RC in the strain R26 makes this mutant more suitable for our investigation because its optical spectrum is simpler than the wild type one lacking the intense absorption peaks of the carotenoids. From *Bioconjugate Chem.* 2023, 34, 4, 629–637.

Reconstituting bacterial photosynthesis in Giant Unilamellar Vesicles

The embedding of isolated and purified RC in biomimetic environments such as liposomes [16] is used to investigate the RC functioning in an environment resembling the physiological one. Recently, the primary generation of chemical energy by molecular machinery was achieved by compartmentalizing the enzymatic systems in giant lipid membranes where RC acted as micro sized transducers for the conversion of light energy into a pH gradient across the lipid membrane [17]. Furthermore, it was possible to reconstitute the RC in giant unilamellar vesicles retaining the vast majority of the enzyme in the physiological orientation of RC, namely $90\pm 1\%$ of the proteins were reconstituted with the same orientation possessed in the photosynthetic membrane. As a consequence, the RC-GUV were able to transduce light energy generating a pH increase inside the closed vesicles [18].

Figure 4. (A) Scheme of RC@GUVs function under red-light illumination. (A) RC is reconstituted in a highly oriented manner (90%) in the membrane of GUVs, whose average diameter is 20 μm. The asterisk marks a non physiologically oriented RC. (B) Detail of the photochemical mechanism generating the pH gradient. hv, light energy. From *Proc Natl Acad Sci.* 2021, 118(7) e2012170118.

A further development was realized by entrapping the isolated intracytoplasmic membrane that, upon separation from the bacteria cell, tends to seal in closed vesicles with a diameter ranging from 60 to 10 nm. These vesicles, also called chromatophores, were encapsulated in GUV and - under continuous illumination - used to produce ATP by exploiting the photosynthetic apparatus. The ATP could be ultimately consumed to drive the transcription of a DNA gene, following the RNA biosynthesis inside individual vesicles [19].

Embedding bacterial photosynthesis in polymers

Among the organic polymers used for embedding functional RC molecules [20], we have focussed our attention on polydopamine (PDA) for its many attractive features. PDA, a dark bioinspired

polymer produced by the self-polymerization of dopamine, was selected for its ability to easily form biocompatible, stable, adhesive films with tunable thickness on a large variety of both hydrophobic and hydrophilic substrates; indeed, its limited biological impact, its excellent adhesivity [21, 22] combined with the presence on the polymer structure of redox-active functional ligands, such as quinones, is a very promising material for hybrid bioelectric applications.

The use of PDA on the surface of RC is an efficient strategy to immobilize photosynthetic enzymes onto the electrode surface [23-25], ensuring both protein integrity and efficient electron transfer from the protein to the electrode surface. The assembly of photoactive RC-PDA onto indium tin oxide (ITO) electrodes occurred by mixing aqueous RC and dopamine solutions in the presence of ITO under aerobic and slightly alkaline conditions without affecting its functionality. Adding redox mediators, it has been successfully used in photoelectrochemical cells. The high density packing of the protein within the film produces a remarkably high, but unstable, photocurrent when the mediators are freely diffusing in the electrolytic solution. A lower but very stable photocurrent having an internal quantum efficiency of 21% is obtained when mediators are encapsulated with the reaction center in the film [24].

PDA forms also suspended nanoparticles (NPs) whose diameter can be controlled by tuning dopamine polymerization conditions such as pH, temperature and monomer concentration but the optical opalescence and the dark color of NPs can limit their use in light-driven reactions of systems based on a (bio)active species embedded in or coupled with PDA NPs. The treatment with ethylenediamine (EDA) has been shown to induce a controlled degradation of PDA, promoting NPs size reduction and significant changes of their absorption and emission properties [26]. The presence of O₂ as an oxidant is crucial for the self-polymerization of dopamine and alternative routes may be of interest for the formation of adhesive polydopamine layers in environmental conditions where oxygen is not available. Recently, PDA polymerization was achieved exploiting the metabolism of the extremely sensitive to oxygen mutant strains R26 of *R. sphaeroides*. The increase of the optical density recorded at different wavelengths, when bacteria are grown in dopamine supplemented medium, implied the contemporary biomass gain and the formation of PDA which absorbs at 588 nm [27].

Using whole, metabolically active microorganisms greatly simplifies the preparation of the biocatalyst avoiding enzyme isolation and purification and potentially enhances stability of the system thanks to their self-repairing and replication features. A one-pot procedure initiated by oxygenic polymerization followed by electrochemical polymerization produced a PDA-redox-mediating matrix enabling photocurrent production in whole bacteria-based biohybrid photoanodes [28].

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